

COMMUNICATIVE AND FUNCTIONAL FEATURES PUNCTUATION MARKS

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Abstract. *The validity of this article and its relevance are justified by the role played by the text, especially fiction, as an object of humanitarian and philological research and thinking. The ability to interpret a text, as many researchers rightly note, allows you to join the author's vision of the world, enrich yourself spiritually, and improve a person's spiritual culture. When analyzing a literary text, the dominant place is usually given to lexical and stylistic means, but syntactic means, which have come to the forefront in modern literature, play a crucial role in creating the expressiveness of the text, in understanding the main idea of the work and the author's worldview.*

Key words: *punctuation, intonation, frequency punctuation marks.*

The effectiveness of developing punctuation literacy depends on the degree of formation of their understanding of punctuation marks. In this regard, we will consider the features of the functioning of each punctuation mark, based on their description presented in the scientific literature.

The period is the most common punctuation mark, which is used to mark the end of an independent sentence. This punctuation mark is an expression of “zero” emotionality if the sentence contains a message (neutral statement) about some phenomenon or event. Question marks and exclamation marks also belong to the group of “end” marks. They fix the end of the sentence and necessarily introduce additional expressiveness and emotionality. To express emotionality, two or three exclamation marks can be used.

The question mark, acting as an indicator of emotionality, is used to express bewilderment, surprise, uncertainty, doubt.

It can be combined with an exclamation, most often when conveying direct speech. These punctuation marks are used both as independent lines of dialogue, and also as a means of expressing an assessment of the components of the content or structure of the text.

The ellipsis has a number of functions related to the transmission of emotional or semantic aspects of the content of speech. As N.S. points out. Valgina, ellipsis can convey hidden meaning, understatement, emotional and psychological stress, difficulty and intermittency of speech. In addition, this punctuation mark can indicate a meaningful break in the text, a transition from one idea to another (usually at the beginning of a paragraph). In the middle of a sentence - to indicate the appearance of something unexpected or surprising in the text.

An ellipsis, just like exclamation and question marks, can be used as a line of dialogue - to indicate the absence of any verbal reaction.

Scientists classify a paragraph (red line) as a sign that has logical-semantic and communicative functions: it divides the text into logical parts, united by meaning, since the frequency of use of a paragraph is largely determined by the goals of the writer, this sign performs an emotional-expressive function in a literary text. According to V.F. Ivanova, this sign is the “most meaningful” of all signs, and its use should be recognized as the most difficult, since there are no rules on how to use it.”

The comma is multifunctional and most often combines grammatical and semantic functions in a sentence: it is used to separate simple sentences within a complex sentence, with homogeneous members of a sentence, to highlight subordinate clauses, isolated members, etc. This punctuation mark also indicates their semantic boundaries. In some cases, the comma has an emphatically semantic (meaning-distinguishing) function (for example, Execution cannot be pardoned). In a complex sentence, a comma indicates a specific semantic relationship between its parts.

A semicolon is a punctuation mark with pronounced grammatical (structural) features. In the case when a semicolon is used instead of a comma to indicate a sharp separation of thoughts, “it begins to act as a meaning distinguisher.”

The colon performs an explanatory function, often with meanings of causality in disclosing the content. At the same time, the placement of a colon after words introducing direct speech is determined not only by the semantic, but also by the grammatical division of the sentence.

The dash is also one of the most common characters in modern written speech. It is used to convey the meaning of opposition, condition, comparison, consequence, etc. This punctuation mark can also be used as an author’s mark with a variety of functions. B.A. Dmitriev expresses the idea that the dash is becoming a universal punctuation mark because if the writer does not know which sign to put, then he puts a dash.

The dash is used in sentences expressing a rapid change of actions and events. This function transforms this sign into the category of stylistic means: it adds dynamism to the statement and indicates the emotional intensity of the speech. In incomplete sentences, the dash as a space sign is characterized by a purely grammatical function.

Quotation marks emphasize the unusual use of the word, highlight it, and also indicate its special emotional and psychological content. In the linguistic literature, the functions of this punctuation mark are defined as follows:

- highlighting a word or expression in order to attract the reader’s attention (highlighting function);

- highlighting a word or expression used in a figurative meaning (preventive function);

- highlighting a word or expression, which allows you to indicate the attitude of the writer to the content of the statement (evaluative-modal function);

- highlighting words or expressions for the purpose of assessing the linguistic means used (metalinguistic function);

- highlighting direct speech and quotes (warning function);

- highlighting words-names (graphical function).

Brackets highlight comments and explanations that complement the main information of the statement. This sign, according to scientists, is the most powerful distinguishing sign that can indicate the informative duality of the statement.

Summarizing the description of the role of punctuation marks in language and speech, we can conclude that punctuation units perform certain functions fixed in the language. The most common of them (emphasis and separation) reflect the grammatical characteristics of punctuation marks (they indicate the boundaries of the components of a sentence as a syntactic unit). But a detailed description of the functions shows that their specific implementation is due to the fact that punctuation marks are used, firstly, to convey a certain component of meaning in a statement (sentence), secondly, to express the emotional state of the author of the statement, and thirdly, to enhance expressiveness of speech (they are able to enhance the significance of one or another component of the meaning of the content of the statement), fourthly, for the purpose of

figurativeness, the creation of one or another image (they are able to convey dynamic action, the tension of the author of the speech, irony, etc.), fifthly, to express subjective modality (the attitude of the author of speech to what is being communicated), sixthly, to convey the logical relationships of the components of the content of the utterance. The above generalization of the particular functions of punctuation marks allows us to assert that their use in speech is associated with the implementation of the communicative intention of the author of the speech. Therefore, they all perform a communicative function.

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